

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract

Objectives

The main objective of this study is to depict the evolution of women as a super power by highlighting her participation in economic activities. Gone are the days in which women were confined inside four walls of the house and attending to domestic activities which has no exchange value ie which are not income yielding. At present she is regarded as super power, participating in economic activities having ownership, being employed and giving employment to many people. Entrepreneurship may be new or inherited, it may be due to passion or urge to solve financial problem in the family. They are undertaken in the areas which are compatible to women like weaving, Tailoring knitting, Aqua culture, mushroom business, apparel, papads and jaggery. To trace the problems of women entrepreneurs Many problems stand in the way of entrepreneurship like shortage of raw materials and unskilled labor non availability of capital for new ventures, marketing problems. The business environment is less conducive for development of Indian entrepreneurs in comparison with international countries. To portray the role of government to foster women entrepreneurs After 1991 huge impetus was provided for their development as it is the only way to eradicate unemployment and poverty. The government started providing many incentives, subsidy and training to stimulate entrepreneurship like TREAD which is Trade Related Entrepreneurship and Development, Mahila coir Yojana, Support To Training and Employment Programmes For Women (STEP) The SIDBI (Small Industries Development Bank Of India) and NSIC (National Small Industries Corporation) have launched many programmes for women Entrepreneurs. The centre has launched E-Hatt to promote women

entrepreneurs..There is positive correlation between enterprenurship and development as it enhances the GDP i.e (Gross Domestic product) of the economy and is the only way to solve the problems created by the growing population. If each one gives employment to atleast one, the demand for job by educated youth would reduce thus bringing equilibrium in the job market with the supply.

DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

This paper analyses the obstacles or challenges in women entrepreneurship. This also make comparison with in india and with international countires by using secondary data which is obtained from World Economic Forum Report,CMIE Report,Global Entrepreneurship Report.

FINDINGS

Women Entrepreneurs are high in USA which is a major cause of advancement. If a self employed person provides employment to atleast one person the problem of unemployment will not exist in the economy. In USA 1 in every 11 adult women is an entrepreneur and women business owners contribute to overall employment of 18 million workers and generate up to 2 to 3 trillion dollars in US economy.

Limitations: This paper uses secondary data

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PAPER

This paper is significant in the wake of unemployment and poverty found in India which is nil or negligible in other countries.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

This paper can inspire women to take up some productive ventures and contribute to the development of the economy.Instead of blaming the Government or destiny for poverty and unemployment .each one especially women can be the owner of an enterprise and stimulate employment to others thereby eradicating the problem of poverty through employment opportunities, The Government can create an environment to foster entrepreneurship.Banks can provide liberal credit for nurturing women entrepreneurs.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This paper can be useful to policy framers to regard women as a potential dynamic contributor of economic growth. women oriented schemes to eradicate the difficulties can be framed for India to be called as a developed country like USA.

The banks play a vital role in fostering entrepreneurships through their schemes

The government supports the women entrepreneurs by giving subsidy and launching schemes like TREAD, STEP and so on.

KEY WORDS

TREAD- trade related entrepreneurship assistance and development.

STEP - support to training and employment programme.

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Women Entrepreneurship means ownership and management of enterprises by women. The outlook of women has been enhanced from traditional to modern as she has been recognized as a super power, with enhanced status by contributing to the development of the economy. India's Five year plans has recognized that women are the agents of change and social growth, as her participation in economic activities is emphasized. women entrepreneurs in developing countries faces many challenges in running of enterprises such as shortage of capital, problems in marketing, decision making, lack of education which are not found in developed countries. The micro and macro environment are conducive to growth and development of self owned enterprises in advanced nations. Women entrepreneurs embraces organized and unorganized sectors, and covers activities like catering ,tailoring ,knitting ,making jaggery , papads , aquaculture. There is a positive correlation between the entrepreneurship and development. This paper highlights the importance of women entrepreneurship as it is the only answer to eradicate the problems of unemployment and leading to growth of the economy.

It makes the comparison between India and international countries with regard to entrepreneurship

This paper states the schemes of the government.

INTRODUCTION

An entrepreneur is one who initiates innovates and creates new products, and process. The Government of India has stated that the financial interest should be 51% of capital and at least 51% of employment should be provided to women for it to be called women entrepreneurship. According to World Economic Forum Report women Entrepreneurship is not new .It is an area in which women have natural expertise for instance food related business like baking ,catering, clothing related like tailoring and boutique, handicrafts ,lifestyle sector business. Women are guided by the pull and push factor like inheritance, passion ,urge ,freedom at work, being a boss on their own and to tide over financial problems ,unemployment. Retrenchment etc. There may be business entrepreneur, trading ,industrial, corporate ,technical women entrepreneurs. They may be in rural or in urban areas. The educated entrepreneurs command a better position than ,the uneducated who are induced out of necessity. They may be inherited or first generational. Their contribution has lead to the growth of the economy. women Entrepreneurship is closely related to economic development.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To trace the challenges of women entrepreneurs
- 2) To state the growth of women entrepreneurs in India
- 3) To provide international comparison of entrepreneurs
- 4) To mention the schemes adopted by Government

BACKGROUND OF THE PAPER

There is a problem of unemployment and poverty. Every year huge number of graduates being added to unemployed list .Employment generation becomes static. The demand for jobs increases and when supply of jobs becomes inelastic, dis equilibrium exists in labor market .To correct this, entrepreneurship is the only way to combat this problem. Men command a

higher position than females in this field as they possess better bargaining and negotiating skills than females in this regard.

METHODOLOGY

This paper uses secondary data from World Economic Forum Report, CMIE Report, Global Entrepreneurship Monitor

The Indian women are nowadays becoming entrepreneur due to employment generation, for financial sustainability, Wealth creation ,economic growth ,to alleviate poverty and to bring about, economic ,social and political empowerment of women .The countries like USA ,Australia and U,K tops the list of women entrepreneurs followed by Denmark and Netherlands. (according to Global Women entrepreneur Leaders scorecard released at Dell Women's Network summit Bangalore) This is due to favorable business climate, equal rights and access of women to education and internet. India occupies 29th position due to many obstacles and challenges which Indian women have to face. The following chart depicts the challenges faced by women.

Act as impediments to development. These obstacles are not prevalent or at minimized level in other countries'. A recent study indicated that women from low and middle income countries enter into entrepreneurship at early stage to supplement their income than those of high income countries. Like Sweden and Belgium. In USA 1 in every 11 adult women is an entrepreneur and women business owners contribute to overall employment of 18 million workers and generate up to 2 to 3 trillion dollars in US economy .

In India the number of entrepreneurs are high in U.P followed by Tamilnadu, Kerala Punjab ,Gujarat ,Maharashtra ,Karnataka and M.P .The table and graph substantiates the statements.

TABLE ON NUMBER OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

State of units	No of women entrepreneurs
Tamilnadu	2930
UP	3180
KERALA	2135
PUNJAB	1618
MAHARASTR A	1394
GUJARAT	1538
KARNATAK A	1026
MP	842

The basic requirement of innovation and entrepreneurship are finance, policy of government, entrepreneurship education ,infrastructure ,and socio cultural norms. The individual attributes are age, gender ,and motivation which has great impact on business growth, innovation and internationalization. These basic requirements are duly fulfilled in advanced countries which brings about an increase in GDP as the nature of entrepreneurial activity is positively correlated with development.

According to GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR

country	Entrepreneurship rate score
U.S	82.9
AUSTRALIA	74.8
U.K	70.6
DENMARK	69.7
NETHERLAND	69.3
FRANCE	68.8
ICELAND	68.0
SWEDON	66.7
FINLAND	66.4
NORWAY	66.3

This clearly shows that US tops the chart followed by Australia, UK, Denmark, Netherlands, France, Iceland, Sweden, Finland and Norway.

GOVERNMENT AND BANKS SCHEMES

TREAD scheme started by the government to provide trade related entrepreneurship assistance and development., Mahila coir Yojana ,STEP ie support to training and employment programmes for women. Programmes are also launched by National Small Industries Corporation (NSIC) and Small Industries Development (SIDBI) for development of women Entrepreneurs. The Government offers subsidies and marketing and training facilities for fostering entrepreneurship. Banks also provide different schemes as

BANK	SCHEMES
PUNJAB NATIONAL BANK	PNB MAHILA UDYAM NIDHI SCHEME
STATE BANK OF MYSORE	STREE SHAKTHI, ANNAPURNA
ORIENTAL BANK OF COMMERCE	MAHILA VIKAS YOJANA
BANK OF BARODA	AKSHAYA MAHILA ATHIKSAHAY YOJANA

CONCLUSION

Women Entrepreneurship plays immense role in developing the Economy. A Nation cannot keep nearly half of its population as weaker sections and move ahead. In countries like USA the percentage of self employed has more than doubled from 14% to 36% from 1960 to 1994 which is a positive change leading to increase in GDP. Similarly if the number of self owned enterprises increases, the problem of unemployment which was created by increase in population can be solved in India.

REFERENCES

CMIE REPORT

GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP REPORT

WORLD ECONOMIC FORUM REPORT